

CHARACTERIZATION OF SINGLE CARBON FIBER MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR BY NANO-TENSILE TESTING

M. Kant¹ and D. Penumadu²

¹Post-Doctoral Scholar

Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Tennessee, Knoxville
851 Neyland Drive
325 John D. Tickle Building
Knoxville, Tennessee 37996-2313
Email: mkant@utk.edu

²Fred N. Peebles Professor and JIAM Chair of Excellence

Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Tennessee, Knoxville
851 Neyland Drive
312 John D. Tickle Building
Knoxville, Tennessee 37996-2313
Email: dpenumad@utk.edu

Keywords: Carbon Fibers, Mechanical Properties, Mechanical Testing, Non-linearity

ABSTRACT

Demonstrated here is a new nano-tensile testing approach which applies small amplitude, harmonic overtone loading ($< 100 \mu\text{N}$) during quasi-static tensile extension. Using this technique, the modulus is probed directly, thus, errors associated with averaging, discrete differentiation, and gripping effects are eliminated, resulting in unprecedented precision in determining elastic modulus, which is a function of strain amplitude, and related fidelity. Applying this new technique to multiple grades of Toray PAN carbon fibers, including T300, T400, T700, T800, M40J, and M50J, a summary of the non-linear stress-strain properties are evaluated. An updated mathematical description of the modulus dependency on strain is documented, which demonstrates a distinctive structure-property link amongst all PAN based carbon fibers. From this relationship, implications are discussed regarding the general behavior of PAN carbon fibers in FRPs and development of new fibers from novel precursors and/or manufacturing processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

The determination of mechanical behavior of single carbon fibers is critical to the performance of Fiber Reinforced Plastics (FRPs) and to the development of new fibers from novel manufacturing processes and fiber precursors. Typically, the axial, elastic properties are determined by either tensile testing of resin impregnated fiber tows (i.e. fiber bundles). Industry has adopted the approach to obtain tensile properties of carbon fibers using a tow of fibers due to its simplicity and ease of sample preparation. However, the tow based tensile test implicitly incorporates deformation processes not resulting from its fiber constituents, such as interface and delamination mechanisms, and thus, does not accurately represent the true stress/strain behavior of a single fiber as shown in Figure 1. Hence, tow based testing cannot be relied upon to make definitive conclusions regarding carbon fiber synthesis techniques and structure to property relationships for single fibers. Although, ultimately it is the goal to use single fibers as fiber tows in FRPs, in practice, the tow based approach is useful for validation of manufacturing process that has been well established and to determine how a fiber behaves in a larger system. A more direct approach for axial, elastic behavior is the single fiber tensile test, but the lack of robust, on-specimen strain measurement forces experimentalists to utilize approximate methods for grip compliance corrections, which have been shown to be increasingly unreliable with larger strain amplitudes [1]. However, by small force dynamic oscillation by

Continuous Stiffness Measurement (CSM), the grip compliance effect has been demonstrated to be minimized, allowing for the measurement of exceptionally accurate axial moduli [1, 2]. Presented here is a summary of a previous publication from the authors demonstrating the CSM testing technique and initial results for high performance carbon fibers, which are known to have a significant modulus dependency on strain [1-8].

$$E(\varepsilon) = E_0 [1 + \gamma\varepsilon] \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Typical tensile test for single fiber and fiber tow, demonstrating unique stress/strain (a) and modulus (b) behavior [1, 9].

2 DYNAMIC MODULI BY CONTINUOUS STIFFNESS MEASUREMENT (CSM)

Tensile tests on single fibers were performed using the MTS Nano Bionix UTM® Universal Testing System (Figure 2). The load sensing apparatus of the Nano UTM is the nano-mechanical

actuating transducer (NMAT). The NMAT column has three main components; an electromagnet, a capacitance gage, and supporting leaf springs, as shown schematically in Figure 2. A deforming sample is attached to the NMAT at one end and is extended at the other by an optically encoded stepper motor with 35 nm resolution in displacement positions. The capacitance gage measures the vertical displacement of the NMAT column, while the electromagnet applies load, either tension or compression. The testing system uses a PID feedback loop to obtain the load on the sample by applying the necessary force to maintain a zero displacement condition in the NMAT's capacitance gage when the sample is extended in tension via the extension axis at the top. This testing system is unique in its ability to apply small, in-situ sinusoidal loads during quasi-static tensile extension. These small sinusoidal loads, maximum of 4.5 mN, are superimposed onto the restoring force necessary to maintain the constant position in the capacitance gage. The corresponding sinusoidal displacements are measured at the capacitance gage, from which a lock-in amplifier determines the phase angle between the applied sinusoidal load and resulting displacement.

Figure 2 - Nano Universal Testing Machine (left) and Nano Mechanical Actuating Transducer (NMAT) configuration (right) [1].

The complex state of stress and strain for a linear viscoelastic material can be expressed as in Eqs. 2 and 3 [10].

$$\sigma^* = \sigma_o e^{i\omega t} + \sigma_r \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon^* = \varepsilon_o e^{i(\omega t - \varphi)} \quad (3)$$

The suffix “r” denotes the restoring stress determined by the feedback loop, and φ is the phase angle between the applied harmonic load and the measured harmonic displacement. Using Hooke’s law and considering the small amount of time that static stress is nearly constant, the complex moduli can be evaluated as below:

$$\sigma^* = E^* \varepsilon^* = (E' + iE'') \varepsilon^* \quad (4)$$

$$E' = \left(\frac{\sigma_o}{\varepsilon_o} \right) \cos(\varphi) \quad (5)$$

$$E'' = \left(\frac{\sigma_o}{\varepsilon_o} \right) \sin(\varphi) \quad (6)$$

where E' is the storage modulus representing applied sinusoidal stress in-phase with strain and E'' is the loss modulus representing the out-of-phase component.

The NMAT in free space, with no sample engaged, can be mathematically represented by a 1-D harmonic oscillator described by the following equation of motion:

$$F_0 e^{i\omega t} = m\ddot{z} + C_s \dot{z} + K_s z \quad (7)$$

where m , K_s , and C_s are the mass, stiffness, and damping in the NMAT column, z is the column displacement, and ω is the frequency of load oscillation. Assuming a harmonic solution as in Eq. 8 and substituting the appropriate time derivatives into Eq. 7, the dynamic stiffness and damping are obtained as:

$$z = z_0 e^{i(\omega t + \varphi)} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{F_0}{z_0} \cos(\varphi_s) = K_s - m\omega^2 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{F_0}{z_0} \sin(\varphi_s) = C_s \omega \quad (10)$$

The natural frequency is approximately 8 Hz for the grip system used in this work. When the sample is engaged, the model is updated to include the sample as a linear spring and dashpot in parallel as the NMAT and sample experience the same harmonic displacements due to the system configuration. Hence, a Voigt solid is chosen to model the viscoelastic behavior of the sample. Using the same procedure as before, the resulting dynamic stiffness and damping with the fiber engaged can be determined as follows:

$$\frac{F_0}{z_0} \cos(\varphi_{S+F}) = K_s + K_F - m\omega^2 \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{F_0}{z_0} \sin(\varphi_{S+F}) = (C_S + C_F) \omega \quad (12)$$

where K_f and C_f are the stiffness and damping of the sample. To extract material properties from the dynamic experiments, the characterization of instrument coefficients is needed, such that Eqs. 9 and 10 are subtracted from 11 and 12. The instrument's stiffness (Eq. 9) and damping (Eq. 10) are measured pre-test when the sample is in a slackened state for each new fiber specimen. This assumes the slightly slackened sample offers no buckling resistance, which is reasonable for high aspect ratio samples, such as carbon fibers and allows for mass fluctuations between tests. The 1-D model, including sample and machine components, is useful for measuring material properties if it accurately describes the behavior of the NMAT and sample, i.e. no additional modes of oscillation are present and the material response is representative of linear viscoelasticity. The authors have thoroughly vetted this assumption in a previous publication to which the readers are referred [1]. All dynamic tests were performed with a harmonic load of 0.040 mN, sufficiently small to avoid fatigue damage to the fiber during tensile extension.

The following equation is used to define the dependency of axial modulus with strain.

$$E(\varepsilon) = (\gamma E_0) \varepsilon + E_0 \quad (13)$$

Here, γE_0 is the slope of modulus with strain and E_0 is the initial modulus. A linear curve fit is used to determine γE_0 and E_0 for each sample as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Example measurement of T800 carbon fiber modulus dependency with strain, γE_0 , from the Continuous Stiffness Measurement (CSM) approach [1].

3 SINGLE CARBON FIBER AXIAL MODULUS BY CONTINUOUS STIFFNESS MEASUREMENT

Previous work has demonstrated increasing axial carbon plane alignment with axially increasing load/strain amplitude, but accurate measurements of fiber moduli with tensile extension have been

limited by standardized techniques [6, 8, 11]. Therefore, the modulus dependency with strain for various types of PAN carbon fibers produced by Toray were investigated by in-situ CSM approach, considering T300, T400, T700, T800, M40J, and M50J fibers. Typical storage modulus with strain relationships acquired by the CSM are given in Figure 4a. All fibers demonstrated increasing modulus with strain. T300, T400, and T700 fibers had similar moduli and modulus/strain relationships, while T800, M40J, and M50J had successively increasing moduli and modulus/strain dependency. T300, T400, T700, and T800 fibers demonstrated excellent modulus linearity with strain in agreement with Eq. 13, but a slight deviation from the linear approximation with respect to strain was observed for M40J and M50J fibers. Hence, the non-linear behavior diminished as the axial modulus of the fiber approached that of single crystal graphite. Softening behavior, documented previously for tow testing approach, was not observed here for any sample, i.e. fibers continually stiffened until failure [6, 9].

Using Eq. 13, γE_0 and E_0 were calculated for multiple single fiber tests, the average values of which are shown in Table 1. Consistently, γE_0 by CSM is greater than that reported previously for similar samples by impregnated tow, confirming the hypothesis that conventional tow testing technique would under-predict PAN carbon fiber modulus dependency on strain due to intrinsic errors associated with tow testing protocol. A unique master relationship is observed for all fibers evaluated in this study by plotting the slope of the modulus with strain, γE_0 , against the initial elastic response, E_0 , as in Figure 4b. The ratio of γE_0 to E_0 was found to be 29.4. This positive correlation was not only observed on a tow to tow basis, but also within a single tow from fiber to fiber, demonstrating the precision of the testing techniques implemented in this study. The linear γE_0 to E_0 relationship from fiber to fiber within a single tow indicates structural differences analogous to that observed amongst all PAN fiber types, specifically greater carbon plane axial orientation and graphitization, in addition to dimensional changes, gage length and/or diameter. In general, this trend suggests the formation of high modulus PAN carbon fibers creates compliant structural pathways, which enable carbon plane reorientation under applied stress. The excellent correlation in Figure 4b would suggest a fundamental process-structure-property relationship of PAN carbon fiber microstructure, linking γE_0 to E_0 , and the following universal constitutive model for PAN carbon fiber modulus is proposed:

$$E(\varepsilon) = E_0 + (29.4 * E_0 - 1010) * \varepsilon \quad (14)$$

Figure 4 - (a) Example of single-fiber modulus to strain relationship for all PAN fibers tested here obtained by CSM approach. (b) The relationship between single-fiber modulus dependency on strain, γE_0 , and initial modulus, E_0 , revealing a strong positive correlation consistent within all tows. In general, the tow based approach produced a reduction of the modulus dependency on strain [1].

Precise fiber properties and their statistical distribution are also essential for multi-scale modeling of composites from mechanical properties of fibers and resin system. The work here suggests the measured statistical distribution of fiber elastic properties obtained within a single tow is due to the effect of structural differences between fibers. Non-uniform fiber mechanical properties within a tow will result in stress concentrations with applied deformation, leading to premature failure and decreased carbon fiber based polymer composite mechanical properties. Thus, at a manufacturing level, the ability to discern the mechanical property distribution of PAN and PAN carbon fibers across the spinneret and at all processing stages, as the techniques here are shown to do, is critical to integrity of the composite part.

Samples	Current Study (single fiber with CSM)			Hughes (Tow) [3]	
	#	E_0	γE_0	E_0	γE_0
T300	29	222 ±11	5537 ±270	220	3300
T400	24	227 ±10	5556 ±238	230	3600
T700	15	224 ±8	5773 ±181	240	3840
T800	29	282 ±14	7173 ±395	270	4590
M40	26	409 ±31**	10732 ±827**	370*	8880*
M50	27	476 ±18**	13201 ±651**	430	11180

* denoted “M40B”

**denoted “M40J” and “M50J”

Table 1 - Comparison of nonlinear elastic properties for multiple PAN fiber tow tensile test with single-fiber dynamic tensile testing [1].

4 CONCLUSIONS

A novel nano-tensile testing system has been developed for performing highly accurate dynamic tensile testing of small diameter (100 nm to 100 microns) fibers. This system is capable of applying simultaneous sinusoidal loading on a deforming fiber under tensile extension, to obtain the dynamic moduli as a function of global strain. The true elastic, axial mechanical behavior as it relates to microstructure is optimally evaluated by the CSM testing technique using single fibers. The CSM moduli are unaffected by system compliance effects, such that on-specimen strain measurement techniques and/or system compliance corrections are not necessary to acquire very precise elastic properties on single fibers. Tensile testing of PAN carbon fibers reported in literature by static single-fiber stress-strain differentiation with a standardized compliance adjustment or fiber tow tests have generally under-estimated the modulus dependency on strain. From our study, the CSM technique demonstrated an increase in the modulus dependency on strain by as much as 30%, when compared to past studies. The technique presented here is useful to obtain the relationship between tensile modulus and microstructure without test protocol ambiguity. A strong, universal relationship between modulus dependency on strain and initial modulus was observed for all types of carbon fibers evaluated in this study, demonstrating an unprecedented sensitivity to structural changes from fiber to fiber. The ratio of γE_0 to E_0 was found to be 29.4, which is observed to be a universally applicable for PAN carbon fibers. In general, the use of CSM moduli has application for all types of single fibers that exhibit significant variation in stress/strain response with time, including high-performance fibers such as Kevlar and ultra-high molecular-weight polyethylene.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported in part by ONR Contract N00014710504, under a program managed by Dr. Yapa Rajapakse and is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Kant and D. Penumadu, Dynamic mechanical characterization for nonlinear behavior of single carbon fibers. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **66**(0), 2014, 201-208.
- [2] C. P. Beetz, Jr. and G.W. Budd, Strain modulation measurements of stiffening effects in carbon fibers. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, **54**(9), 1983, 1222-1226.

- [3] J.D.H. Hughes, Strength and Modulus of Current Carbon-Fibers. *Carbon*, **24**(5), 1986, 551-556.
- [4] G.J. Curtis, J.M. Milne and W.N. Reynolds, Non-Hookean Behaviour of Strong Carbon Fibres. *Nature*, **220**(5171), 1968, 1024-1025.
- [5] C.P. Beetz Jr, The analysis of carbon fibre strength distributions exhibiting multiple modes of failure. *Fibre Science and Technology*, **16**(1), 1982, 45-59.
- [6] M. Shioya, E. Hayakawa and A. Takaku, Non-Hookean stress-strain response and changes in crystallite orientation of carbon fibres. *Journal of Materials Science*, **31**(17), 1996, 4521-4532.
- [7] T. Ishikawa, M. Matsushima and Y. Hayashi, Hardening non-linear behaviour in longitudinal tension of unidirectional carbon composites. *Journal of Materials Science*, **20**(11), 1985, 4075-4083.
- [8] I.M. Djordjević, D.R. Sekulić, M.N. Mitrić and M.M. Stevanović, Non-Hookean Elastic Behavior and Crystallite Orientation in Carbon Fibers. *Journal of Composite Materials*, **44**(14), 2010, 1717-1727.
- [9] Y. Zhou, M.A. Baseer, H. Mahfuz and S. Jeelani, Statistical analysis on the fatigue strength distribution of T700 carbon fiber. *Composites Science and Technology*, **66**(13), 2006, 2100-2106.
- [10] A.S. Nowick and B.S. Berry, *Anelastic relaxation in crystalline solids*. New York and London: Academic Press, 1973.
- [11] D. Loidl, H. Peterlik, M. Müller, C. Riekkel and O. Paris, Elastic moduli of nanocrystallites in carbon fibers measured by in-situ X-ray microbeam diffraction. *Carbon*, **41**(3), 2003, 563-570.